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ABSTRACT

This document shows the results on the plant C input results for grassland systems in Europe in response to changes in two key drivers: (1) land-use change and (2) management practices and change. This report adds to the currently available data on plant C inputs and here the focus is upon European grassland systems

WP4. Grassland management

DELIVERABLE - WP4.4. C-input rates for grassland measures

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1. Summary

This document shows the results on the plant C input results for grassland systems in Europe in response to changes in two key drivers: (1) land-use change and (2) management practices and change. This report adds to the currently available data on plant C inputs and here the focus is upon European grassland systems

2. Introduction

One of the key drivers for SOC-sequestration is an enhanced input of biomass to the soil. Indeed there is great importance to improve the estimates of plant inputs given the effects of climate change. In fact, Wiesmeier et al. (2016) stated that plant C inputs have to increase by 29% to maintain present SOC stocks in agricultural soils. However, detailed management data comprising estimates of C inputs to soil is still challenging, accordingly C-input by aboveground and root biomass may be evaluated by reverse modelling with the RothC model. The reverse modelling allows to determine emission factors and simple response function to extrapolate SOC change for other grassland field.

This document reports on the simulated **plant carbon (C) inputs** estimated using the RothC model (for details see Deliverable 4.3). These results are based upon a dataset which is mostly from **long-term experiments LTE** (see Deliverable 4.2 for details).

3. Results

3.1. Plant carbon inputs - Overview

Simulated plant carbon inputs (t C/ ha/ yr) were estimated from **long-term grassland experiments** in seven European countries. There were a total of **298 estimates** of plant carbon inputs which corresponds to 298 unique treatments from all of the experiments.

A summary of the simulated plant carbon inputs with specific treatments given in Table 1. The results are split into the two main groups:

Land management

- (i) permanent grasslands (no change in land use over decades) and having received a “Nutrient **Management**” (fertilisation, see DL 4.1) and

Land use change

- (ii) grasslands established following a **land-use change from cropland** (control crop)
- (iii) grassland receiving a **silvo-pastoral systems** established from existing grassland (control grassland having not trees).
- (iv) forests experiencing a **land use change to agroforestry with grass** (control forest having no grass).

The experiments with land use included management treatments and those with management treatments did not include any differences or changes in land use. The treatment effects and mean value for each treatment shows that there were no overall effects of land use or management. For a comparison of the specific land use types a significant effect was detected ($P = 0.03$). Three different type of management (control, mineral fertiliser and farmyard manure/ slurry) were found to be significantly different.

Table 1. A summary of the simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ ha/ yr) values for selected land use and management measures from long-term grassland experiments in Europe

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Plant inputs (t C ha/ yr)	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	210	2.97	0.10	0.38
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	88	3.16	0.26	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	33	2.44	0.40	0.03
2 ^a	Grass LUC (control)	28	4.36	0.55	
2 ^a	Agroforestry	21	2.84	0.28	
2 ^a	Grass	2	2.51	0.13	
2 ^a	Wood	3	3.3	0.60	
3 ^b	Remaining grass (Control)	22	3.17	0.20	0.006
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	175	2.86	0.11	
3 ^b	Farmyard manure/ slurry grass	13	4.11	0.23	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were management treatments tested

Table 2 provides the mean simulated plant carbon inputs for the seven countries evaluated. Table 3 provides the mean simulated plant carbon inputs according to the different WRB soil orders (WRB, 2015).

Table 2. A summary of the simulated mean plant Carbon input values (t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) for different countries based on long-term grassland experiments in Europe

Countries	n	Plant inputs (t C ha/ yr)	SE
France	22	2.31	0.24
Germany	63	3.34	0.32
Netherlands	10	5.02	0.63
Spain	3	4.38	0.78
Sweden	2	1.89	0.54
Switzerland	13	4.68	0.33
UK	185	2.77	0.10

Table 3. A summary of the simulated mean plant Carbon input values (t C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) for different WRB soil orders from long-term grassland experiments in Europe

WRB soil orders	n	Plant inputs (t C ha/ yr)	SE
Andosol	2	4.25	0.17
Arenosol	2	1.68	0.40
Cambisol	76	3.78	0.27
Fluvisol	12	1.63	0.22
Cambisol	2	1.89	0.54
Gleysol	6	4.25	0.52
Haplorthod	4	6.18	1.23
Luvisol	184	2.73	0.10
Regosol	3	1.71	1.08
Umbrisol	3	4.38	0.78

There were sufficient data to evaluate the simulated plant carbon inputs specific to two countries: Germany and the United Kingdom. Table 4 shows the simulated plant carbon inputs for the different treatment factors in Germany and also for the United Kingdom in Table 5. In addition, an evaluation of the Cambisol soil order was undertaken and the simulated plant carbon inputs are given in Table 6 for that soil type.

Table 4. A summary of the simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values for selected land use and management measures for grasslands in Germany based on long-term experiments

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Plant inputs (t C ha/ yr)	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	22	3.1	0.26	0.58
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	41	3.47	0.47	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	26	2.63	0.50	0.048
2 ^a	Grass	14	5.04	0.89	
2 ^a	Wood	1	3.42	NA	
3 ^b	Remaining Grass (Control)	26	3.33	0.25	0.98
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	37	3.35	0.52	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were management treatments tested

Table 5. A summary of the simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values for selected land use and management measures for grasslands in the United Kingdom based on long-term experiments

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Plant inputs (t C ha/ yr)	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	169	2.78	0.10	0.90
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	16	2.73	0.33	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	4	1.63	0.22	0.10
2 ^a	Grass LUC (control)	4	3.12	0.64	
2 ^a	Agroforestry	3	4.07	0.75	
2 ^a	Grass	2	2.51	0.13	
2 ^a	Wood	2	3.24	1.03	
3 ^b	Remaining Grass (Control)	11	2.92	0.20	0.0005
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	145	2.64	0.11	
3 ^b	Farmyard manure/ slurry grass	13	4.11	0.23	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were management treatments tested

Table 6. A summary of the simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values for selected land use and management measures for long-term grassland experiments with a Cambisol soil type

Treatment group	Treatment	n	Plant inputs (t C ha/ yr)	SE	P values
1	Land use (No) & Management (Yes)	39	4.15	0.20	0.158
1	Land use (Yes) & Management (No)	37	3.39	0.50	
2 ^a	Arable LUC (control)	21	2.57	0.59	0.245
2 ^a	Agroforestry	1	4.18	NA	
2 ^a	Grass	13	4.77	0.97	
2 ^a	Wood	1	4.28	NA	
3 ^b	Remaining Grass (Control)	26	3.33	0.25	0.98
3 ^b	Mineral fertiliser grass	37	3.35	0.52	

^aThis group of treatments is for experiments where there was a land use change or difference in land use

^bThis group of treatments is for experiments where there were management treatments tested

3. 2. A comparison between simulated plant C inputs and environmental and physical explanatory factors

The simulated plant C inputs are compared with several factors which can potentially be considered explanatory factors; this includes annual mean rainfall (mm), annual mean temperature (°C) and the soil clay content (%). These are displayed in the figures (1-10) below according to the country or the soil order. Each data point represents a land use or a management treatment at a LTE site.

Figure 1. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and annual mean rainfall (mm) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

Figure 2. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and annual mean rainfall (mm) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to WRB soil orders)

Figure 3. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and annual temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

Figure 4. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and annual temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to WRB soil order)

Figure 5. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and mean clay content (%) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to the WRB soil order)

Figure 6. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and mean clay content (%) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven European countries)

Figure 7. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C /ha/ yr) values and annual temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to seven different European countries)

Figure 8. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C /ha/ yr) values and annual temperature (°C) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to the different WRB soil orders)

Figure 9. A comparison between simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values and mean clay content (%) for long-term grassland experiments in Europe (according to the different WRB soil orders)

Figure 10. Simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values for selected long-term grassland experiment sites in Europe

4. Discussion

4.1. Management effects

Studies with different management treatments ('measures') were studies where there was also no land use treatment. Evaluation of all the data with a management treatment (and no land use change) had a smaller simulated plant carbon input (2.97 t C ha^{-1}) compared with where was no management (3.16 t C ha^{-1}) (with land use change), but this difference was significant ($P = 0.38$; see Table 1). There was a significant ($P = 0.006$) management effect when comparing the three main management measures: grass control, mineral fertiliser and farmyard manure/ slurry (Table 1). The size of management effects is very large and the wide range of simulated plant carbon input values can be observed in Figure 1 that shows C inputs and annual rainfall. For instance, at a single LTE site there was a constant amount of annual rainfall and in many cases this corresponds to a range in C input values. The same pattern in the data can be observed in Figure 3 which plots C inputs with annual mean temperature. The comparison between environmental variables (Figures 1-10) shows that at a single given site there is significant potential for management to increase the plant carbon inputs. It is possible that environmental variables such as rainfall is an important driving factor which has a positive effect on plant carbon inputs, however further work is required to confirm this. Poeplau (2021) reported that intensive grasslands which receive mineral fertiliser has a positive effect on SOC stocks. Results here show that overall (i.e. all data; Table 1) and in the United Kingdom (Table 5) the greatest plant Carbon inputs were for the farmyard manure/ slurry treatment which was approximately 1 t C ha^{-1} higher than the mineral fertiliser treatment. There are potential issues with plant carbon inputs from organic nutrient sources such as slurry. Don et al. (2024) warn that the supply of organic mater from manure can potentially be described as leading to indirect C sequestration, because the source of C is from other sites. This transfer of C has been described as a form of C leakage (Paustian et al., 2019). These simulated plant C inputs show that management is a an important measure with a significant impact on potential soil C sequestration. Future research on the management related factors on plant carbon inputs and their relative impact is required. For this to be achieved a larger dataset with an increased spatial coverage is essential.

4.2. Land use effects

Studies with different land use treatments ('measures') mostly were studies with no management treatment. Evaluation of all the results showed that there was no land use effect (Table 1). This was misleading though and a more detailed comparison in Table 1 shows the different type of land use and between these types of land use there was a significant difference. Where grass was a control the plant carbon input had the highest value (4.36 t C ha^{-1}) which was significantly higher than the arable control (2.44 t C ha^{-1}). Geographic/ spatial differences in the land use effect were found by comparing the results from Germany (Table 4) and the UK (Table 5). A land use effect was detected for the data from Germany, but not for the UK data. The importance of spatial variability can be observed in the different simulated plant carbon inputs according to soil orders (Figure 2). Moreover, the differences across Europe can be observed in the simulated plant carbon inputs in the map for the whole of Europe (Figure 10). The results in this study illustrate that land use and land use change is a key factor which strongly influences plant carbon inputs and this in turn can significantly effect SOC stocks.

The impact of land use has been reported previously. For instance, an in-depth evaluation of land use and the study of grass or grass leys in crop rotations. Johnston et al. (2017) reported annual increases in the SOC (%) were only possible with the inclusion of grass or grass+ clover leys or the application of FYM; in contrast, there was an overall decrease in SOC for an all arable rotation. The effect of grass

leys on plant carbon inputs was not simulated in this study, however the findings by Johnston et al. indicate that this is a worthwhile area of future research.

Meersman et al. (2013) published 14 crop-specific C input values for France. The differences which Meersman et al. reported between the crops was large. Consequently, it is possible that the large variation observed in this study are due to different types of grassland. Further evaluation of these data could identify specific plant input values according to grassland type.

4. 3. Spatial variability in plant carbon inputs

Future evaluation of these plant C input estimates must account for the spatial differences across European grasslands (Figure 10). Unfortunately, it was only possible to statistically evaluate two countries: Germany and the United Kingdom (Table 4 and 5). Maillard et al. (2017) clearly demonstrated that increasing spatial scale is a major factor in the uncertainty of SOC stocks in grasslands. Without a large increase in suitable data from LTE there is a need for alternative methods to improving understanding on plant carbon inputs. Alternative datasets can be considered such as the LUCAS data (see Del. 4.5.)

4. 4. Modelling uncertainty

The simulation of plant C inputs are always associated with a level of uncertainty. The classical inverse method to apply RothC is based upon a spin-up with a SOC stock value for the starting year of a given period (Coleman and Jenkinson, 1996, Coleman et al., 1997). Because there was no starting year SOC stock value for most LTE studies it was decided to spin-up using the final (or end) year SOC stock value. For a small selection of data records ($n = 106$) a comparison was undertaken on those studies where both starting and end SOC stock values were available. We found that using the end SOC stock values for the spin-up underestimated the plant C inputs compared to using the starting SOC stock. The mean difference between the simulated plant C inputs based on a spin-up with a starting year SOC stock was 138% compared to using an end year SOC stock value. This difference corresponds to an additional $1.3 \text{ t C ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$. The overall difference covered a wide range of values from a minimum of 87% to a maximum of 226%. Fig. 11 shows the simulated plant C inputs for studies where both starting and end year SOC stock values can be compared.

Figure 11. Simulated mean plant carbon input (t C/ha/yr) values for selected LTE's according the starting year SOC stock value (○) and the final/ end year SOC stock value (●) for spin-up

One of the fundamental problems with simulating plant C inputs relates to the uncertainty regarding whether steady-state saturation exists or has been observed (Stewart et al., 2007). Fornara et al. (2016) reported increases in SOC stocks from a long-term experiment in Northern Ireland where there is no evidence of SOC saturation.

4. 5. Areas of future research

Long-term experiment data

One of the major limitations of this study was the lack of suitable grassland long-term experiment (LTE) data. The deficiency in SOC data was in several respects. First, for the purposes of estimating SOC stocks and simulating plant C inputs for European grasslands there is a poor geographic coverage. In Deliverable 4.1. we reported that 465 suitable data records were collected from eight countries. There are several regions within Europe with no data; for example: the Mediterranean, Scandinavia and Eastern Europe. The focus of this project was to collect published data from LTEs, however the resulting lack of data indicates that other sources of data should be investigated.

We recommend that future research investigates the use of data from national soil surveys or monitoring schemes. Using national level data would pose harmonisation issues for a Europe-wide evaluation, however it might ensure that there is improved spatial coverage across Europe. Many countries undertake monitoring projects which include the measurement of SOC in grasslands. The Countryside survey in the UK is a suitable example of national monitoring survey which has been used to evaluate soil C sequestration (Reynolds et al., 2013). Likewise, the French soil monitoring network (RMQS) has been using to estimate C input in France (Meersmans et al., 2013). There some disadvantages from using national level data and it can be difficult to bring national data together for a Europe wide assessment due to differences in method, sampling depth or the time of sampling.

There has been considerable interest in evaluating data from European scale surveys such as LUCAS. There have also been some efforts to harmonise soils data from national networks and LUCAS (Froger et al., 2024). Further discussion on some published results with a focus on grassland using the LUCAS data is given in Deliverable 4.5.

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